

Background Movement Effects in Tracer-diffusion in Pure and Soil Systems

(Miss) S. BANDYOPADHYAY and S. K. SANYAL

Department of Agricultural Chemistry & Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya,
Kalyani-741 235

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Tracer-diffusion experiments in pure and soil systems have been conducted in order to provide an experimental test of the predictions regarding ionic (background) movement in tracer-diffusion. The effect of valency of tracer cation on such background movement has also been investigated, and the results agree, at a qualitative level, with those predicted theoretically.

IN recent years, theoretical considerations based on irreversible thermodynamics have predicted a movement of the uniform background, present in excess, in self- and tracer-diffusion experiments in soil¹. We have further demonstrated² that the magnitude of such background movement should depend on the valence ratio of the tracer and the background cations. A knowledge of this movement, if any, is essential in detecting and quantifying the errors that ensue in D-values obtained with the assumption of a stationary background^{3,4}. The present paper describes experimental tests, examining the possible background movement, first in pure three-component (aqueous) diffusion systems of the type KCl-NaCl-H₂O and then extends such studies to soil systems with emphasis on the aforesaid valency effect.

Theoretical The relevant theoretical treatment has already been given^{1,2,5} and only a brief outline is sketched here. Thus, Fick's first law for a complete description of solute flows (J) in a three component system^{2,5} as encountered in tracer-diffusion of, say, CaCl₂ in a uniform KCl solution reads,

$$J_1 = -D_{11} \left(\frac{dC_1}{dx} \right) - D_{12} \left(\frac{dC_2}{dx} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$J_2 = -D_{21} \left(\frac{dC_1}{dx} \right) - D_{22} \left(\frac{dC_2}{dx} \right) \quad (2)$$

with $D_{12} \neq D_{21}$. The subscripts 1 and 2 represent Ca²⁺ (tracer) and K⁺ (it is immaterial if they alternatively denote CaCl₂ and KCl¹). It has been already demonstrated^{1,5} that D_{11} and D_{22} , the straight diffusion coefficients, approach (for the present case) the tracer-diffusion coefficient of Ca²⁺ and the binary diffusion coefficient of KCl (at the given composition), respectively, while D_{12} and D_{21} , the "cross-effect" coefficients, exhibit interest-

ing behaviour. Thus, while D_{12} approaches zero (for $C_1 \rightarrow 0$), D_{21} has a limiting value given by^{2,5},

$$D_{21} = \frac{-D_2 [Z_1 Z_2 C_2 (D_1 - D_3)]}{Z_1 (Z_1 D_1 - Z_3 D_3) C_1 + Z_2 (Z_2 D_2 - Z_3 D_3) C_2} \quad (3)$$

where, Z_1 denotes the valence (including sign) of the ion 'i' and the subscript 3, which appears in addition to 1 and 2 already introduced, refers to the common anion (e.g. chloride in the present case). It is thus apparent from equations 1 and 2 that the background movement ($J_2 \neq 0$) should initially arise ($dC_2/dx=0$) from a non-zero value of D_{21} .

For tracer-diffusion ($C_1 \rightarrow 0$), it follows from equation 3,

$$D_{21} \approx - \frac{Z_1}{Z_2} \left[M \lambda_{m_2}^0 \left(\frac{\lambda_1^0 - \lambda_2^0}{\lambda_{m_2}^0 + \lambda_{m_3}^0} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

in which λ_i^0 is the limiting (equivalent) ion conductance of the *i*th ion and $\lambda_{m_i}^0$ its limiting molar conductance ($\lambda_{m_i}^0 = |Z_i| \lambda_i^0$). Equation 4 is based on the Nernst's expression for limiting ionic diffusion coefficient, namely,

$$D_i^0 = \frac{RT}{F^2} \lambda_i^0 \times 10^{-7} \quad (5)$$

where, F is the Faraday's constant.

It may be worth considering here that a positive value of D_{21} (which is equivalent to $\lambda_{m_1}^0 > \lambda_{m_2}^0$ as pointed out earlier²) indicates the background migration in the direction of tracer-diffusion, while a negative magnitude of D_{21} that in the reverse direction. Furthermore, equation 4 suggests that the background movement effect should become

more appreciable as the valence ratio of the tracer and background cations (for a given tracer electrolyte) becomes wider in a series of diffusion studies employing background electrolytes with comparable molar conductances.

Experimental

The chemicals used, such as $\text{ZnCl}_2 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, KCl, NaCl, CaCO_3 , HCl were of AnalaR and/or G. R. grade. Conductivity water, having specific conductance less than $3 \mu \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, was used in the preparation of the solutions. The soil was a laterite soil (collected from Susunia, West Bengal) having a pH 4.5.

Diffusion experiment in pure solution : Diaphragm cells with arrangements for magnetic stirring of the type close to that designed by Stokes⁷, were used. The cell was made from a glass tubing of internal diameter 2.3 cm. The vertical cell was divided into two compartments by a Pyrex G-4 sintered glass disc. The compartments above and below the diaphragm had volumes of 45.8 and 48.0 ml, respectively. The air-thermostat used was a wooden box having as components an electric bulb (100 W), an electric fan and an electrical contact thermometer inserted through a hole. The box was insulated from the surroundings with polystyrene foam on the inside of the front wall having a door that can be opened whenever necessary. The temperature was maintained constant at $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$. While mounting the diffusion cell in the appropriate position inside the thermostat, due care was taken to keep the diaphragm within 1° of the horizontal position. The solution-filled methodology was followed in the present case thereby eliminating the inconveniently long pre-diffusion period for establishing the steady state in diaphragm⁸.

The systems studied were the aqueous solutions of (i) NaCl (background) with KCl or CaCl_2 (tracer), and (ii) KCl (background) with NaCl or CaCl_2 (tracer). At the end of the appropriate diffusion periods, the solutions from both the compartments were withdrawn and the background concentrations (e.g. Na^+ or K^+ concentration) were estimated flame photometrically.

Diffusion experiment in soil : The diffusion cells were assembled by bringing in contact two half-cells each of which was a cylinder (3.7 cm i.d. \times 1 cm) open at both ends and made from a perspex block. The end of each cylinder, not in contact with the other half-cell, was supported against a bakelite sheet with a groove cut in the latter so as to hold tightly the half-cell. After the two half-cells were gently brought together, these were held in position by tightening the screws across the supporting pair of sheets.

The diffusion cells were uniformly packed with soil equilibrated with NaCl or KCl (6200 ppm on soil basis) along with a small amount of, e.g. CaCl_2

(100 ppm on soil basis) in one half-diffusion cell marked A, and the other (marked B) with only NaCl or KCl equilibrated soil. For NaCl or KCl treatment (for both the half cells A and B), the soil was equilibrated with excess of the salt several times by wetting and drying followed by wetting; excess of the salt was then drained off and wetting and drying cycles continued at least 6 times more. Then the solution containing tracer cation was added to small portions of soil and wetting-drying cycle run twice more (for the A-half only). However, because of experimental difficulties with as heterogeneous a system as soil, it was not possible after final wetting to obtain exactly the equal concentration of background cation in the soil samples for half-cells A and B, even though the difference was negligibly small.

Required amount of water (to satisfy the water holding capacity of the soil) was added to the half-cells which were placed in a humidicator for thorough mixing. On forming the complete diffusion cells, diffusion was allowed in an incubator, and after appropriate periods, e.g. 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9 and 10 days, the corresponding diffusion cell was dismantled and Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} were extracted from soil in both the half-cells with double-distilled water.

The sodium and potassium contents of the extract were determined flame photometrically while calcium by atomic absorption spectrophotometer, and any background movement was finally estimated from the results. The plausible valency effect of the tracer cation on such movement was also ascertained.

Results and Discussion

The results in pure as well as soil systems investigated reveal a background movement of cations as evidenced by a non-zero value of the difference of (water extractable) background cation concentrations (ΔC_B) between the two half-cells at all periods of diffusion. While for pure solutions, only such migration of the background cation was ascertained, for soil systems investigated, it was further confirmed that with the passage of diffusion period, the resultant ΔC_B of the background cation used narrows down as a consequence of migrations in the opposite direction, arising from the induced ΔC_B (Fickian diffusion; *vide* Figs. 1 and 2). In some cases such ΔC_B values even attain a final time-independence. It may, however, be noted here that with the initial ΔC_B between the two half-cells not being zero (because of experimental limitations as mentioned earlier), one would expect some background movement in soil systems initially; nevertheless, any further movement beyond a period corresponding to $\Delta C_B = 0$ certainly arises from coupling with tracer diffusion, thereby rendering ΔC_B again attain non-zero values (Figs. 1 and 2). Table I summarises the movement of background cation in the direction as indicated for tracer

Fig. 1. Background movement in tracer-diffusion in Susunia soil ; diffusion system : (∇) KCl (background)-CaCl₂ (tracer) and (◻) KCl (background)-NaCl (tracer).

Fig. 2. Background movement in tracer-diffusion in Susunia soil ; diffusion system : (⊙) NaCl (background)-CaCl₂ (tracer) and (Δ) NaCl (background)-KCl (tracer).

TABLE 1

Background-tracer system	Order of the limiting molar conductances of background and tracer cations	Migration of background electrolyte from*
KCl - NaCl	K ⁺ > Na ⁺	bottom-half to top-half
KCl - CaCl ₂	Ca ⁺⁺ > K ⁺	top-half to bottom-half
NaCl - KCl	K ⁺ > Na ⁺	top-half to bottom-half
NaCl - CaCl ₂	Ca ⁺⁺ > Na ⁺	top-half to bottom-half

*According to theory $(\lambda_m^0)_{Background} > (\lambda_m^0)_{Tracer}$ should induce a background movement from bottom-half to top-half of the diffusion cell (Ref. 2).

diffusion studies in pure systems. In each of the two cases, the top-half of the Stokes' diaphragm cell contains a minute amount of the diffusing tracer electrolyte.

As regards the soil systems studied, the migrations of background cation observed are presented in Table 2. In each case, the A-half was tagged with the tracer and brought in contact with the B-half.

TABLE 2

Soil	Background-tracer system	Order of the limiting molar conductances of tracer and background cations	Migration of background electrolyte from*
Susunia	KCl - CaCl ₂	Ca ⁺⁺ > K ⁺	A to B
	KCl - NaCl	K ⁺ > Na ⁺	B to A
	NaCl - CaCl ₂	Ca ⁺⁺ > Na ⁺	A to B
	NaCl - KCl	K ⁺ > Na ⁺	A to B

*According to theory, $(\lambda_m^0)_{Background} > (\lambda_m^0)_{Tracer}$ should induce a background flow from B-half to A-half of the diffusing cell (Ref. 2).

The results obtained in the present study and interpreted as above, therefore, suggest that the background in self- and tracer-diffusion experiments may not be considered stationary and appropriate corrections are to be applied to the self- and tracer-diffusion coefficients calculated from soil diffusion studies based on such assumption of a static background. The observed directions of background (cation) movement have also generally been in agreement with those theoretically predicted² (Tables 1 and 2). It is of interest to mention here that such background movement has earlier been reported from this laboratory² for tracer-diffusion in sand, a non-interacting medium of intermediate nature between pure and soil systems.

Re-examining the cases of these tracer-diffusions, we find at times (during the initial stages of tracer-diffusion) corresponding to $\Delta C_B = 0$ (i.e. $\frac{dC_2}{dx} = 0$),

$$J_2 = -D_{21} \frac{dC_1}{dx} \text{ (from equation 2)}$$

A measure of J_2 at this stage or immediately afterwards, will thus be given by any ΔC_B that results as a consequence of such J_2 (which, however, for a short time period hence, may be assumed not to change dC_2/dx substantially from its zero value). Further, the concentration gradient of the tracer, dC_1/dx , may also remain virtually unaltered over such short periods immediately after the start of diffusion. That is to say, the resultant ΔC_B may well be taken to provide an approximate measure of D_{21} for the given system.

Referring to Figs. 1 and 2, such times for reckoning ΔC_B (which are close to diffusion periods corresponding to $\Delta C_B=0$) turn out to be, approximately, 4.8 and 19.2 h for tracer-diffusion with KCl and NaCl background, respectively, in Susunia soil and the corresponding ΔC_B values are noted from Figs. 1 and 2. The latter lead to the relative values of D_{z1} for the systems, and are recorded in Table 3

TABLE 3—VALENCY EFFECT OF TRACER-ION ON BACKGROUND MOVEMENT

Soil	Background (X)- tracer (Y or Z) system	Observed ΔC_B ratio for the diffusion systems, $\frac{[\Delta C_B]_{x-y}}{[\Delta C_B]_{x-z}}$ (vide. Figs. 1 and 2)	Theoretical $\frac{(D_{z1})_{x-y}}{(D_{z1})_{x-z}}$ (vide. eqn. 4)
Susunia (laterite)	$\frac{\text{KCl-CaCl}_2}{\text{KCl-NaCl}}$	1.33 (20/15)	1.30
	$\frac{\text{NaCl-CaCl}_2}{\text{NaCl-KCl}}$	10.33 (77.5/7.5)	1.011

which also enlists the ratios of the D_{z1} values to be expected theoretically (from equation 4) for these

various diffusion systems studied, in order for providing a comparison and a test of equation 4. The last two columns of Table 3 reveal an excellent concordance between the ratios of ΔC_B values observed and those of the corresponding theoretical values of D_{z1} , and is thus considered satisfactory.

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